

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN NURSING THERAPEUTICS

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Abstract:

Many of us read and hear that the goal with AI is to teach and expand knowledge worldwide, which can lead to improved treatments and better healthcare outcomes.

It seems there is a fear of the unknown, as AI is not fully developed in healthcare.

There are definitely some pros and cons, and hopefully we will figure out an algorithm of success for both healthcare providers and consumers.

Can each one of us confidently accept the challenge?

Yes...if we leverage advancements in technology married with enhanced clinical delivery capabilities we can dramatically improve services provided to patients.

Some open challenges in embracing this newer learning are logistic concerns, data driven decision making, end to end task completion not being available in certain clinical settings for AI applications, lack of availability of curricula ready nurses etc.

Today nurses have expanded roles and are taking care of patients with needing complex care with high acuity ensuring shorter hospital stays. Many non-nursing, repetitive and mundane tasks like hunting and gathering etc. can be done with help of AI.

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Introduction:

The subject of discussion here is **How can Nurse leaders be prepared in the “Use of Artificial Intelligence(AI) in Nursing Therapeutics”**. To Link the concept of AI to Nursing Therapeutics, it is important to understand this terminology.

“Nursing therapeutics is a term devised to describe how student nurses can exploit the therapeutic potential of any patient contact especially when related to specific and routine

nursing interventions” (Richardson, Percy and Hughes , Nurse Education Today 2015). Last year , in the United States of America, the government agencies have been asked to implement strategic objectives aimed at speeding up AI research and development. So AI is very much securing its place in the forward view.

The virtual branch:- The virtual component is represented by Machine Learning. **Deep learning** is a subset of **machine learning** where **artificial neural networks**, algorithms inspired by the human brain, learn from large amounts of complex data.

Deep Learning:

This computer science approach consist of networked algorithms called *neural networks* where neurons are networked in our brain. In deep learning, a set of mathematical instructions such as an algorithm, which is called a *node*, works like a neuron to fire the algorithm, action it as instructed, and relay the information to another node in the computer.

That algorithm is then used as input by another node in the neural network. Data move through the nodes in a direction specified by the algorithm. A deep learning model can contain billions of nodes embedded in many layers. This stacks algorithms in a hierarchy of increasing complexity and abstraction. Put simply, deep learning is all about mimicking the brain and using neural networks with more neurons, layers, and interconnectivity. And when we read about advances in computing from driverless cars to Go-playing supercomputers to speech recognition, that is deep learning secretly in action.

Deep Learning in Application:

Molly, is a virtual nurse developed by Senseley. She is described as having the capacity to provide remote monitoring and support for common and high-cost medical conditions. Molly is provided as part of a health plan that is aimed at healthcare providers. It is also extended to third-party payers such as employers.

Molly, represented as an avatar on screen, can show statistics like weight and blood pressure generated from bluetooth-connected Molly monitoring devices. This app and its connected devices can be used to monitor congestive heart failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and similar conditions.

From home, a patient can manage his condition by monitoring weight, blood pressure and general health with the use of Molly. As shown, Molly is capable of speech recognition and verbal responses to the patient’s query. It also comes with a chatbot in

case the patient to needs to discuss health matters privately. Patients can also send images to human healthcare providers through Molly. A search tool helps health plan members find nearby treatment options. Patients can download the software on IOS or Android phones. The 2-minute video demonstrates how Molly helps remotely manage patients who have been discharged from hospitals but still need monitoring and support (De Jesus, 2019). <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cMN6vwQErGQ>>.

Researchers around the globe are creating robots to help people drive, impact suicide rates, support clinical telehealth applications, and more. This is all associated to ‘Deep Learning’. Human-like robot nurses or nursebots are already being used to support healthcare workers in some parts of the world such as in Japan. The lack of healthcare workers and an increasingly aging population has made nursebots imperative with regards to assisting elderly clients, carrying out tasks such as physically moving them, assisting in daily tasks such as bathing, dressing, socialising with simple conversations. This will trigger a change in the role of nurses in care delivery.

Are the Leaders Ready?

Why would Leaders vote for AI to be included in Nursing Practice and Education?

Sophia, the first social humanoid robot has won our hearts so much that she has gained a citizenship in Saudi Arabia.

The benefits that are appealing to leaders are:

- Fills the gap with the shortage of Nurses as ‘Manpower’ world wide
- Reduces the workload of Nurses
- It is ‘Fatigue’ proof!
- An answer to occurrences of ‘Human Errors’
- Several studies show ‘Patient Satisfaction’ to these provisions made available to them
- Can be economical in the long run
- The scope in Nursing Education and Training of student nurses

Of course, there are several benefits that the Nursing field and our leaders can exploit and it is already doing it in many ways as we have seen. cutting-edge technologies save time, money and serve patients more efficiently. It would permit nurses to spend more time at the bedside and gain a better understanding of the patient's illness and needs

The scope in Nursing Education and Training is immense. Nurse Leaders are looking for ways and means to tackle the lack of ‘the availability’ of clinical placements with the need for nurses only growing stronger. Using ‘Deep Learning’ can support and assist in

projecting various clinical situations in a safe environment and in laboratory settings through the use of Robots. Creation of diverse scenarios that requires critical thinking and appropriate actions fits in well with “disrupting the students equilibrium to trigger their learning and movement till they understand it” (Race) There is a gap between what students know and what they don’t know. AI can be hugely beneficial in building that bridge between known and unknown and replace some of the clinical hours required in practice.

Beginning in 2011, the field started to see leaps in progress, with advances in computer processing capabilities. Computer scientist Andrew Ng proved that ‘computers can learn what an object is without being told what it represents’. However his research incorporated the use of 10 million online videos of cats. Over time, the computer learned what a cat was. This quantum leap technology is currently used in speech recognition systems. This means that leaders must regard the resource of cost, time and equipments

Are there enough data scientists with the expertise in using AI in healthcare? Along with data scientists, nurses may need to be pulled into this team to help design and deploy new applications. Although it would mean losing nurses from practice and education, it would still increase the scope of nursing.

In an organisation, having a mindset that is progressive is necessary for the momentum to take pace in the deployment of AI. Prepare and training professionals and teams to learn new ways to collect and use patient data and information should be considered.

Ethical considerations- In the current scenario a key concern of AI users is managing bias. If computer algorithms are trained using biased information (probably of the engineer who set it up), they'll give back biased results. Another aspect of bias to consider is the issue of algorithm transparency: Does the AI system have the capability to explain the results back to the user? The user must understand and analyse how the computer reached its decision when installing new technologies i.e. “How are the results are tracked to judge the accuracy of recommended decisions?” (Turek)

What if AI makes a mistake with a wrong nursing diagnosis or clinical decisions? How will Leaders manage the safety quotient? Who will be responsible for the false results and where does the liability stay? These are difficult answers that lay huge accountability on Nursing Leadership. So, updating pertinent laws, standards, and protocols will be necessary as AI is introduced to the Nursing Fraternity.

It is vital for Nursing Leaders to recognise the shift ‘not towards the complete replacement of nurses’, but towards symbiosis and joint collaboration with AI. AI could serve as a ‘third eye’ for nurses in clinical practice. There is significant evidence that suggest that Intuition is a key aspect of human decision-making and can be explained as a process where analytical and non-analytical reasoning processes continually interact; thereby, it does not become a replacement for ‘Medical Intuition’.

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